

ANALYSIS AND PLANNING SALES PARTNER SALES SYSTEM FOR B2B PRODUCTS WEB BASED ON INDOSAT OOREDOO LTD.

Engga Prasty¹, Dwi Rachmat Putra², Mira Dwi Rifanti³

¹Department of Information System Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta 11480, Indonesia

Abstract: The application of technology and information has developed significantly and evolved into an information system that is essential for human performance. Sales activities within a company can be developed through information systems, generating profits that significantly impact the company's success. The case study will be conducted on Indosat Ooredoo Ltd., one of the largest telecommunications companies in Indonesia. In the B2B segment, sales can be conducted directly (*Direct Selling*) by Indosat salespeople. Another method involves using sales partners (*Partnerships*) who have undergone an assessment by Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. management. The *Direct Selling* method has been in operation for quite some time, so the business processes and information systems provided are adequate and can be monitored. However, sales using the *Partnership* method are currently still conventional, especially during the reporting process. Sales data and sales results are currently reported manually using MS Office. Partners themselves still find it very difficult to monitor their sales results in *real time*. On the other hand, management also finds it difficult to analyze and make decisions regarding the performance of the partners themselves. Based on these problems, Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. requires a sales information system that aims to store, monitor and display sales results in order to bring up sales partner performance against the given targets.

Keywords: Dashboard, Key Performance Index, Kanban

*Corresponding author: Department of Information System Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta 11480, Indonesia

Engga Prasty engga.prasty@binus.ac.id

Received: 19 June 2021

Dwi Rachmat Putra dwi.putra002@binus.ac.id

Accepted: 19 June 2021

Mira Dwi Rifanti mira.rifanti@binus.ac.id

Cite as: Prasty E, Putra DR, Rifanti MD. Analysis and planning sales partner sales system for b2b products web based on Indosat ooredoo Ltd.

1. Introduction

The application of technology and information has developed significantly and evolved into information systems that are essential for human performance. Supporting information systems in human work can facilitate the processing, presentation, and retrieval of information quickly and accurately. A good and appropriate information system can help an organization maintain its stable existence (Sa'idah et al., 2019). A company's sales activities can be developed using an information system. Sales are crucial for generating profits, which significantly impact the company's success. Accurate, high-quality information that can be viewed in *real time* is fundamental to a company's needs. Therefore, an information system is really needed as a tool to help monitor and make decisions at various managerial functions and levels to improve company performance (Rizki, et al., 2014).

The case study will be conducted on Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. which is one of the largest telecommunications companies in Indonesia. Founded in 1967, PT Indosat Tbk (Indosat Ooredoo Ltd.) is a leading provider of telecommunications network services, telecommunications services and information technology and informatics and/or convergence technology services in Indonesia under the brand name "Indosat" which later became "Indosat Ooredoo Ltd." in 2015. As a member of the Ooredoo Group of global telecommunications service providers, Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. provides cellular services, fixed data and wireless broadband services as well as fixed telecommunications services or fixed voice services including IDD, fixed wireless and fixed lines and digital services (Financial report, 2019) Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. has two business processes, namely *Business to Business* (B2B) and *Business to Customer* (B2C). The company's revenue contribution has been achieved from the B2C segment by 75% and the other 25% comes from the B2B segment. In the 2019 financial report, Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. established a corporate strategy to accelerate B2B as a growth engine, B2B sales again experienced strong growth, supported by various initiatives to become a digital partner and *enabler* of choice for companies and governments.

In the B2B segment, sales can be conducted directly (*Direct Selling*) by Indosat sales representatives . Another method involves using sales partners who have been assessed by management of Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. The *direct selling* method has been in operation for quite some time, so the business processes and information systems provided are adequate and easily accessible. However, the *partnership* sales method faces a different situation: there's no information system for tracking sales results, and the reporting process currently relies on Microsoft Office Excel.

Processing and reporting sales results is time-consuming due to the large amount of data that must be processed and summarized daily. Under these conditions, MS Office Excel is ineffective and inefficient in meeting these needs. Partners themselves still struggle to monitor their sales results in *real time*. On the other hand, management also struggles to analyze and make decisions regarding sales partner performance. Sales partner performance is assessed using parameters provided by Indosat Ooredoo Ltd.. These parameters are then compared against monthly targets to obtain a final KPI that reflects sales partner performance .

Based on these issues, a sales information system is needed that can be used as a tool for sales partners and Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. management to visualize all the necessary tools for monitoring and reviewing sales trends and performance. The web-based information system can be easily accessed by Indosat management and each sales partner.

System development was conducted using agile methods with the Kanban model. In general, agile itself is a method that helps project teams work efficiently, think more effectively, and make decisions quickly. The Kanban model was chosen because it applies agile principles , allowing users and team members to visualize each stage or flow in completing a project, making it directly visible to them (Stellman and Greene 2015).

2. Objective

The objective of this research is to design an information system that can make purchase orders and delivery status from prepaid SP which can make it easier for sales partners and Indosat management to know the number of products that have been distributed and a system that can display an assessment of sales partners using KPI (*Key Performance Indicator*) which is a tool for sales partners in tracking & observing the performance of their sales.

3. Research Method

The research method applied in this research is:

3.1 Data Collection Method

3.1.1 Literature study

To obtain some of the necessary information and data, a literature study was conducted to find supporting theories from journals, e-books, and guidebooks on Database Systems and Agile Methodology that support the writing of this thesis.

3.1.2 Observation

Conducting observations at Indosat Ooredoo Ltd. in the Business Partner division to Seeking information related to ongoing business processes.

3.1.3 Interviews

Conduct interviews with relevant parties to gather the necessary information. The purpose of the interviews is to understand the current situation.

3.2. Analysis and Design Methods

3.2.1 Database System Design

1. Conceptual design is the design of a database that is built with use information as needed
2. Logical design is the process of designing a database based on what is needed based on a relational model, but still stands alone against a

particular DBMS.

3. Physical design is used to describe the storage structure and access methods used to achieve efficient access to data.

3.2.2 System Design

In implementing the development of this system, the author uses the *agile* kanban method. In the development process, this kanban method is adopted from various fields, the kanban method is widely used because it can facilitate a work process. The stages of system design in this study are:

1. *Planning (Estimating, Scheduling, Tracking)* , namely the planning stage, describes the estimated technical tasks to be carried out, possible risks, resources needed to create the system, the work results to be produced, the work schedule to be implemented, and tracking the system work process.
2. *Design* namely This stage is the stage of designing and modeling the system architecture. Design data structures, user interface displays, and programming algorithms.
3. *Construction (Code & Test)* namely the stage of changing the design form into code.
4. *Deployment (Delivery, Support, Feedback)* is the stage of implementing software to *customers*, evaluating software, and developing software based on *the feedback* provided so that the system can continue to run and develop according to its function.

3.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.3.1 Login Page

The login page has the same appearance for the three *users* , namely *manager*, *sales partner* and admin.

Figure 1. *User Login Display*

3.3.2 Pre-Order Request Page

This page is specifically accessed by sales partners to place prepaid card purchase orders.

Figure 2. Pre-Order Request Page Display

3.3.3 Pre-Order Data Page for User: Partner

On the Pre-Order page for *partner users*, the status of the Pre-Order that has been requested will be displayed.

ID	Request Date	Partner	Package	Qty	Ammount	PO Status	Invoice Number	Transfer Receipt	Date Upload	Payment	Production Status	Delivery Status	Distribution Date	Action
11	2021-01-29	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	30	Rp 750,000	Approve	121328			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				
10	2021-04-06	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	123	Rp 3,075,000	Approve	121326		2021-04-06 13:33:24	Verifying Payment				
9	2021-04-03	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 45k	1	Rp 45,000	Approve	121325		2021-04-06 08:33:52	Done	Ready for Service	On Process		
8	2021-04-03	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 90k	1	Rp 90,000	Approve	121327			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				
7	2021-04-03	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	123	Rp 3,075,000	Reject								

Total Count 5

Figure 3. Display of the Pre-Order List Page for Users: Sales Partner

3.3.4 Pre-Order Data Page for Users: Manager

On the Pre-Order data page for manager users, a list of new Pre-Order requested by partners will be displayed. The manager will then take action on the incoming Pre-Order requests, deciding whether to approve or reject the orders.

ID	Request Date	Partner Name	Package	Qty	Ammount	PO Status	Action
16	2021-01-18	BYAKTA DIGITAL EKOSISTEM, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 90k	100	Rp 9,000,000	waiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
15	2021-01-21	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 45k	50	Rp 2,250,000	waiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
14	2021-01-21	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 45k	50	Rp 2,250,000	waiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
13	2021-01-01	FUNBIT SERVIS INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	50	Rp 1,250,000	waiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
12	2021-01-15	ELKOMINDO GLOBAL NETWORK, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	100	Rp 2,500,000	waiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

Total Count 5

Figure 4. Pre-Order List Page Display User: Manager

3.3.5. Pre-Order Data Page User: Admin

On the Pre-Order page for the admin user, it will display Pre-Order that have been confirmed as *approved/ rejected* by the user manager. The admin will make *updates* to change the status of the Pre-Order that has been ordered.

Request ID	Request Date	Partner	Package	Qty	Ammount	PO Status	Invoice Number	Transfer Receipt	Date Upload	Payment	Production Status	Delivery Status	Distribution Date	Action
19	2021-02-17	FUNBIT SERVIS INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 90k	200	Rp 18,000,000	Approve								<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
17	2021-02-09	SHAKILA SUKSES, CV	Pro Freedom Biz 25k	20	Rp 500,000	Approve	121329			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
16	2021-01-18	BYAKTA DIGITAL EKOSISTEM, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 90k	100	Rp 9,000,000	Approve	121334			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
15	2021-01-21	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 45k	50	Rp 2,250,000	Approve	121330			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
14	2021-01-21	SAHABAT TELEKOM INDONESIA, PT	Pro Freedom Biz 45k	50	Rp 2,250,000	Approve	121331			Please Check Your invoice and upload Transfer receipt				<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

Total Count 15

Figure 5. Pre-Order Tracking Display

3.3.6 Partner Performance User Page: Manager

On the *partner performance page*, it will display *performance* that can be selected based on the *partner name* and *partners* as a whole. The *performance* displayed consists of a *KPI performance table*, *gross added activation*, *revenue*, and *churn performance*. Performance is displayed on a monthly basis.

Package Name	Churn Date					
	Total	Jan-21	Feb-21	Mar-21	Apr-21	May-21
Churn Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Freedom BIZ 25	0	0	0	0	0	0
Freedom BIZ 45	0	0	0	0	0	0
Freedom BIZ 90	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 6. Partner *Performance View Page*

4. Conclusion & Suggestions

4.1 Conclusion

Conclusion Based on the results of the analysis and design of the *sales partner* sales system for WEB-based B2B products at Indosat Ooredoo Ltd., the following conclusions and solutions can be drawn:

- The designed *sales partner* information system can facilitate management in assessing sales performance, *sales trends* and *sales partner KPI performance*.
- The sales information system has a feature that can monitor SP (*starter pack*) deliveries, which can facilitate *sales partners*.
- By using the *agile kanban* method, the information system design process becomes easier to monitor work *progress*.
- The need to analyze sales data can be displayed using tables and graphs. In this study, the visualization technology used is still not optimal and can still be developed.

4.2 Suggestions

Based on the system design that was carried out, several suggestions were made. Things to note in developing this system are as follows:

- *Sales partners* can use data visualization and sales graphs *Tableau* technology to optimize analysis needs.
- Requires the development of an information system that can provide *end-to-end business process* features from the initial *sales partner* nomination process to the *sales partner commission calculation process*.
- Information systems that can be integrated with *data* warehouses owned by Indosat Ooredoo Ltd..

References

Rizki, I., Priadi, RAS & Yuniati, Y., 2014. Creation of a Web-Based Sales Information System (Case Study at Ali Computer Store). *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, VIII(1), pp. 37-44.

Sa'idah, N.,Sutanta, E.,Lestari, U., 2019. Nasa Product Sales Application System on Stokies E.1377. *Script Journal*, Vol 7(2); 2338-6313.

Stellman, A, Greene, J. 2015. *Learning agile understanding scrum, xp, lean and kanban*. 1st edition. United States of America. O'Reilly Media.